

International Conference on **ICGB 2017** Green Banking Perceptions and Challenges

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Sustainable Development and Environment Management through Green Banking: A Study with Special Reference to Nationalized Banks in India

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Abstract—The most complicated issue that the world is facing today is climate change. It is due to environmental degradation. The balance in ozone layer is depleting day-to-day. Thus, to preserve & protect environment "Green Banking" is introduced in the financial sector. Every Bank across the globe is adopting green practice. Green Banking refers to those guidelines to make Banking sector environment friendly & reducing the use of carbon footprints. The society has gone "Green" for these aspects. It helps to create effective & efficient solutions for environmental issues. This reviews the secondary data collected from various sources. These types of Banking aims at avoiding paperless work & rely on automation services. It reduces pollution activities. These provides initiatives with nationalized Banks like State Bank of India, Punjab National Bank, etc. The 'Equator Principles' are framework for determining & managing environmental issues. These principles are adopted voluntarily by Financial Institutions. Indian Banks are adopting innovative approach in their strategy process. This will provide sustainable future for Green Banking. The study highlights sustainable Development & Environmental Management through Green Banking.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Ethical Banking, Green Practice, Nationalized Banks & Equator Principles

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is the most complicated issue the world is facing today. Environmentalism is wide way of thinking idea's and social change regarding involvement for environmental protection for effective state of environment. In response to the present discourse of progress that over exploits our nature for economic prosperity. To measure & mitigate the risk of climate change caused by human activity, there have been continuous endeavors across the globe. Sustainability is the key issue. Due to global warming, the rapid change in climate have direct impact on our bio-diversity, agriculture, forestry water resources & human health. To mitigate climate change, many countries have made commitment necessary. There is a need to promote certain measure for sustainable development and corporate social responsibility. Green movement for protection of environment has brought about a change in the way. Business is managed it's towards green economy where everyone are concerned about the environment. Green is the word now Green computing, Green Banking, Green strategic Management and so on. The environment and its concerned are represented with 'color' 'green'. Global warming, also called as "Green House Effect" is a global issue that calls for a global response. Man-Made gas emission such as carbon-dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide & hydro-fluro carbon is responsible for distortion of climate changes. To avoid falling in such traps the call "going green" is running faster among the Indian Incorporations In the

environment friendly society "Go Green mantra" has become relevant in each & every aspect of business. This change with all business activities not only focus on profit but also on people & planet. This way of doing finance are as "Green Banking", a change by the banks to grow and develop industries Going Green and to preserve the natural environment. The principle of Green Banking will be useful to the banks, industries and the economy. Green Banking will make certain that the greening of the industries in accordance with the facilities of developing the qualities of assets of the banks in upcoming times.

CONCEPT OF GREEN BANKING

Green Banking is also called as Ethical Banks, which involves all the social & environmental factors. Therefore they are always called as Ethical Banks. These Ethical Banks have been started with the aim protecting by the environment. They are controlled & managed by the same authorities as that of normal bank. These Banks considers all the social & environmental ecological factors which aims at preserving environment & conserving natural resources it promotes environmental friendly practices & reducing carbon footprints from banking activities. Green Banking helps to create and provide effective and far-reaching market based solutions to inform a wide range of environmental problems including climatic change, deforestation, air issues & biodiversity loss, while at the same time identifying and securing opportunities that benefit customers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the Green Banking concept.
- To study the Benefits of Green Banking.
- To identify Laws and guidelines for Environmental conservation & Sustainability.
- To identify the different level of Green Banking initiative taken across the India.
- To Know the future of Green Banking.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper reviews the literature on the basis of secondary data collected from various sources such as articles, research papers, annual reports, sustainable reports, company's official website etc. for analyzing the Green Banking initiative taken in India top performing banks are selected in both public and private sector.

BENEFITS OF GREEN BANKING

1. It avoids paper works and rely on automation and online banking which can help our environment.

2. It introduce green finance, green marketing, green cards, green mortgages and green strategic planning.
3. It changes the negative impact on society.
4. Green Banking aims at social safety and security of environment.
5. Green Banking gives priority to investments/ loans.
6. Green Banking supervises its member for reducing pollution activities.
7. It increases GDP of the country by reducing the cost and energy.
8. It protects environmental degradation and ensures sustainable banking practices.
9. Creating awareness to business people with the environmental and social responsibility.
10. It is an proactive idea that enables eco-friendly business practices which benefits the upcoming generation.
11. It is a vision for future sustainability.
12. It promotes forest and water preservation, recycling and eco-tourism.

LAWS AND GUIDELINES FOR ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION & SUSTAINABILITY

EQUATOR PRINCIPLES

The Equator Principles are a credit risk management of basic structure for discovering the facts, informing and controlling environmental & social risk in particular purpose of finance transactions. The Equator Principles are accepted voluntarily by Financial Institutions. In the projects, these framework aims at managing various environmental and social risks. Equator Principles are designed to work as a basic base line and for execution by adopting institution of its own internal, social and environmental ideas, methods and Environmental standards related to its project financing. Now at present, 80% Financial institutions have adopted the Equator Principles. In the emerging market, they covers 70% of the International Project Finance debt.

Ex: YES BANK INDIA & HSBC GROUP

The Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP)

The CDP is an UK based organization that works with shareholders and corporations to inform the greenhouse gas emissions emitted by the major corporations. CDP administers annual questionnaires to big companies and related entities who are responsible for the management and investment in order to highlight the risk of climatic changes. It is an

independent non-profit organization which maintains the largest data base on the climate change. The Signatory of CDP are SBI, HDFC Bank Ltd, Reliance.

CERCLA

Comprehensive Environmental Response, Compensation & Liability Act of 1980 (CERCLA) is US based federal law intended to clear the contaminated sites with dangerous substances as defined as "Pollutants". Under CERCLA, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) can conduct a cleanup and seek clean up costs from liable parties. Many Banks have faced loss when found responsible for the pollution performed by them under CERCLA.

BSE GREENEX

Bombay Stock Exchange has Introduced Equity index Known as "BSE-GREENEX" That measures the quality of carbon emission of the companies. "BSE-GREENEX" index has been collaborated with IIM Ahmadabad. This index aims at those investors who are concerned with the environment. They pay investments in companies for better return. Based on energy and financial data, this index will access the energy efficiency of firms.

GREEN INITIATIVES TAKEN BY NATIONALIZED BANKS IN INDIA

RESERVE BANK OF INDIA (RBI)

According to reports of RBI as a part of Green initiatives/practices has asked to ship all the NBFC's to electronic payment system. it has been followed by all the financial sectors. As a result, maximum utilization of available resources will be useful for Government. It has eliminated the post-dated cheques & use of cheques in their daily transaction. This results in faster and accurate settlements of transaction. Being a part Green Banking, RBI has officially issued guidelines to take Specific steps. As a results Banks like, NABARD, SIDBI, EXIM Bank etc. take up the e-governance initiative in a efficient manner. The quality & efficiency of the service will improve & banks will gradually use less paper based transactions.

PUNJAB NATIONAL BANK

The Bank has completely improved the core Banking Solutions to Green Banking. As PNB is the leading financial institutions, it recognized the health of the economy vests on healthy planet. These Green Initiatives promoted rainwater harvesting, reducing the use of paper by e-mailing inter-office communications. It started using energy efficient appliances and conducting the electricity auditing. It placed guidelines for producing renewable energy for supply of commercial projects. They introduced paperless dealing & procedure with speeder communication system through e-network which reduces cost and time. They introduce "Green practices" to conserve resources and "Green audit" towards suitable practices. PNB

uses solar UPS at selected ATM's (in state UP & Bihar). Its opting green practices such as energy efficient lights, printing both sides of paper etc. Further, it has signed "Green Pledge" of the Ministry of New & Renewable Energy. It promotes steps for sustainable development.

STATE BANK OF INDIA (SBI)

SBI, the Biggest and Largest commercial Bank of India has become the leading bank in the country to adopt new activities into transforming its banks into green power. It is the largest sector in terms of market capitalization, profit, net profit revenue & assets. The Bank has introduced a scheme known as 'Green House'. Under this scheme, they are offering concessions on home loans. It supports its clients & offers finance on priority:

- SBI has installed windmills in TN, Maharashtra & Gujarat as a part of Green initiative of capacity of
- It has initiated the disclosure of carbon in financial sectors, for environmental safety & concern.
- It has introduced SMART, ie. Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Time bound for Green Banking goals.
- It intends to bring down the carbon footprints & save environment & energy by initiating Green practices like GCE, Automated Teller Machine (ATM), CDM (Cash Deposit Machine), Green Home loan, Mobile Banking, SMS Unhappy Scheme, Rainwater Harvesting Projects etc.
- Moreover, the bank has launched "GB policy" & decided to run ATM's on solar energy to reduce their power consumption.
- SBI has undertaken several environmentally & socially sustainable initiatives across the country. This bank have been one of the few banks to have started the Green Banking Policy since 2007 across the country.

CANARA BANK

Green Banking is an active way to preserve energy & protection of environment. The main benefit of this approach is conservation of the natural resources:

- Canara Bank has adopted environmental friendly steps like tele-banking, mobile-banking, Solar powered biometric operations, pass book printing kiosk, ATM, Cash/ Cheque acceptor. Etc...

- They are providing due preference & weightage to projects which earns carbon credit like solar energy project, windmills etc.
- To reduce paperwork, the bank has implemented e-governance for HRM functions.
- It is not extending any finance units for producing chloro fluoro carbon, aerosol products, solvent etc.
- To install water treatment projects, they ensure that the borrower to obtain No Objection Certificate (NOC) from central board.

FUTURE OF GREEN BANKING

Indian Economy is an emerging economy and it has a huge potential of growth of Indian banks by adopting innovative approach in their strategy. By setting up of the business model, there is a need of an approach towards paradigm shift which considers all the three aspects of triple bottom line approach. They are the people, planet and the profit. The future of Green Banking in India seems to be very pleasing and promising, as they are expecting lots of green product and services in future.

Green Banking is creating a new trend of it in this financial world. It is a form of banking, taking into account the social and environmental impacts and its mean motive is to protect and preserve environment and natural resources. Being a new philosophy, many countries across the globe have accepted them in their day-to-day financial activities successfully.

Some of the things like Green Excellence awards and recognitions, Green Insurance, Green Investments funds, Green rating agencies, and Green Accounting and disclosure would be heard and seen in operation in the future generation. This Green Banking will act as a check or guide the polluting industries if implemented properly. It can act like guidelines towards economic information and transformation. It will create a platform where many opportunities for financing and investing. And it will contribute towards creation of low carbon economy.

If these, system of banking are implemented properly and adopted a proper strategy process, it will encourage the environmental friendly behavior everywhere. Thus, the future generation will have a good success in economy and the future of Green Banking will proceed on, creating an awareness among the financial sector.

CONCLUSION

Green Banking refers to the initiatives taken by the banks to encourage environment friendly investment. Green Banking has become a buzz in today's banking world. Green

Banking is not only an awareness but it has been made them as their practices. These banks are ensuring efficient utilization of budget allocation as well as for green finance, green event & green project.

Green Banking refers to the term that involves practices & framework to makes banks acceptable in economic, environment & social dimensions. It is an avenue of reducing pollution and protecting environment by aiding sustainable growth. Green Banking is a proactive way for future sustainability. Banks plays an major role undertaking environment and ecological aspect as a part of their conceptual principles. Green banking invest in environmental management.

Green Bank is at start-up mode in India. It has made a framework for sustainable development. Indian banks are greening their activities by adopting green practices. The endeavor will help them to improve their environmental performances and creating values of their business. A System of incentives is an important element for the progress of Green Banking.

Green Banking is a prime new way of planning towards sustainability. It is very important for banks to be pro-active and increase the rate of the growth of the economy. Banks should apply morality of sustainability and responsibility to their business model. It should formulates strategy for their products and services. Thus, it can be concluded that, adoption of Green Banking approach is becoming environment-friendly in addition to benefits like contributing towards environment, enhancing reputation of the bank, reducing the use of carbon etc. In a broad sense, it services as the commercial objectives of the bank and corporate objective towards society. It is necessary to understand the duties towards environment as well as society to compete and servicing in the world wide market. Finally, it could be concluded that going green should be the motto of all commercial banks as it is pro-active and smart way of thinking towards future sustainability.

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